

under irrigated transplanted conditions in Telangana region, A.P. (except in the endemic gall midge-prone areas).

Hari is characterized as follows: medium duration (135-140 d); semidwarf (93 cm); erect, compact, and nonlodging with dark green foliage; no anthocyanin pigment; long (10.14 mm)

slender grain with a kernel length (7.35 mm):breadth (2.08 mm) ratio of 3.54; flinty, white, translucent, nonglutinous grain; no white belly; 1,000-grain weight 25.2 g; protein content, 7.14%; hulling, milling, and head rice recovery, 80, 74.5, and 68%, respectively; good cooking quality. It is tolerant of blast, tungro

virus, sheath blight, and brown leaf spot diseases and green leafhopper, leafhopper, and stem borers. A distinguishing characteristic is a long flag leaf that grows far above the panicle and remains green even after maturity. □

MW10, a promising short-duration variety for western West Bengal

D. Bhattacharya and S. Ghosh, West Bengal Comprehensive Area Development Corporation, 6A, Raja Subodh Mullich Square (9th floor), Calcutta 700013, West Bengal, India

Purulia, Bankura, and Western Midnapur districts of West Bengal are mostly rainfed rice monocropped Jul-Oct (kharif). In spite of average annual rains, extended breaks in rainfall often occur at critical growth stages. Acute water stress significantly reduces rice yields on lateritic soils with high infiltration in an undulated terrain. The problem becomes severe when

Average yield and some agronomic characteristics of MW-10 and other rice varieties in on-farm trials, West Bengal, India.

Variety	Effective tillers/hill (no.)	Grains (no./panicle)	Duration (d)	Av grain yield (t/ha)	AV yield/d (kg/ha)
MW10	13	103	100	2.8	28.0
IET1444	9	110	117	2.5	21.2
Palman 579	8	125	120	2.8	23.6
IR36	12	99	122	2.9	23.8
CR126-42-1	9	93	105	2.8	26.5
IR50	18	104	110	2.1	19.3
IET2815	10	124	114	2.7	23.6
LSD (P=0.05)	2.7	18	6	0.2	1.5

transplanting is late.

We evaluated the promising new variety MW10 against six short-duration transplanted varieties, including locally grown Palman 579, IR36, and IET1444, in six farmers' field trials, in a

randomized block design with four replications. MW10 performed consistently better than the other varieties (see table). Its short duration allows a following short-duration pulse or oilseed crop. □

Improved rice varieties released in North Central Thailand

V. Varamisra, L. Chankasam, K. Sirivong, S. Suwanatane, and T. Sa-nguansaj, Phitsanulok (PSL) Rice Research Center, Phitsanulok 65130, Thailand

Two PSL breeding lines—Phitsanulok 60-1 (PSL 60-1) and Phitsanulok 60-2 (PSL 60-2)—were released in 1987.

PSL 60-1, a high-yielding, photoperiod-sensitive variety is from a three-way cross among Khao Dawk Mali 105, Nahng Mon S-4, and IR26 (KDML 105/NM S-4//IR26). The cultivar is tall with long, slender, clear grain, low amylose content, and good cooking quality. During 1981-85, it averaged 3.48 t/ha, 12% higher than KDML 105, a standard variety (Table 1). It is moderately resistant to bacterial blight, sheath rot, ragged stunt virus,

Table 1. Grain yield and quality of PSL 60-1 and PSL 60-2. Phitsanulok, Thailand, 1987.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)	% increase over check	Grain characteristic					
			Length (mm)	Chalkiness (%)	Amylose (%)	GC ^a	GT ^b	ER ^c
PSL 60-1	3.48	12	7.30	0.24	17.1	S	L	1.64
KDML 105	3.12	—	7.46	0.31	13.7	S	L	1.70
PSL 60-2	4.73	17	7.30	0.98	29.6	H	I/L	1.58
RD 1	4.05	—	7.34	1.05	30.0	H	L	1.70

^a Gel consistency. S = soft, H = hard. By the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (SES). ^b Gel temperature. L = low, I = intermediate. By SES. ^c Elongation ratio (the ratio of the length of cooked rice to raw rice).

Table 2. Reaction of PSL 60-1 and 60-2 to diseases and insects.^a Phitsanulok, Thailand, 1987.

Variety	Reaction ^b to									
	BI	BB	ShB	ShR	YOLV	RSV	GLH	BPH	WBPH	GM
PSL 60-1	S	MR	MS	MR	VS	MR	MS	MR	MS	MR
KDML 105	S	S	MR	MR	VS	S	MS	S	MS	S
PSL 60-2	MR	MR	MS	R	MS	MS	MS	MR	MS	—
RD1	MS	S	MS	—	S	VS	MS	S	MS	—

^a BI = blast, BB = bacterial blight, ShB = sheath blight, YOLV = yellow orange leaf virus, RSV = ragged stunt, GLH = green leafhopper, BPH = brown planthopper, WBPH = whitebacked planthopper, GM = gall midge. ^b By SES: VS = very susceptible, S = susceptible, MS = moderately susceptible, MR = moderately resistant, R = resistant.